

B2-InF Progress Report

In the last months the B2-InF consortium has been working on STAGE 1 of the project, focusing on collecting information from society about their perspectives and knowledge on ART as well as from clinics regarding their current services and approach.

The **main challenge in the project's fieldwork has been data collection** owing to the nature of the substantial qualitative study that had to be carried out in eight different countries across Europe, including around 160 semi-structured interviews. This meant that eight different fieldwork teams were required, working in eight different contexts. To homogenize the data collection process, two handbooks were developed initially.

The **handbooks** were meant to develop 1) a **shared interview methodology** among the research groups and 2) a **training session for the interviewers**. Two training sessions were carried out in parallel, one for Western European countries (Belgium, Italy, Switzerland and Spain), led by **APLICA Coop**, and one for Eastern European countries (Albania, Macedonia, Kosovo, and Slovenia), led by **Healthgrouper**. The training mainly consisted in explaining to interviewers the **aims of the project and the objectives to be achieved through the data collection process**. In addition, the training sessions gave thorough information on how to appropriately fill out the documents to achieve consistency among the data collected.

Ten to fifteen interviews were conducted in each country in vernacular languages and subsequently translated into English. Interviewees were selected following specific criteria, according to variables previously set by the project. Selected subjects were 18 to 30 years of age, including men, women and other genders. Much effort has been put to obtain a sample in each country, including people of different sexual orientations, religions and levels of education. However, this was not always possible, as, in each country, the laws and culture dictate the sample. Each research team was in charge of selecting the sample in their context, leveraging on their networks. This means that **the sample was not randomized, but was an intentional sample** (something common and applicable in qualitative research) **aiming to capture different discourses around the topic and different mindsets**.

With the interview data collection completed, B2-InF is now moving on to its thematic analysis. The consortium is very pleased with the results so far, with much appreciation for the hard work of APLICA and its significant efforts in conducting such complex coordination in close collaboration with Healthgrouper.